

LEARNING IN COOPERATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: The article discusses the actual problem of teaching dialogue speech in English lessons .

Key words: competence , creative activity , method.

We are called upon to prepare students for life in the world of adults, where the ability to cooperate and jointly solve tasks becomes important. In the sample curriculum for the "English" discipline, several goals are clearly defined. In the first place, of course, you can put forward the following goals:

- Formation of communicative competence that allows you to communicate fluently in English in various forms and on various topics.

- Upbringing of a personality capable and willing to participate in communication at the intercultural level.

- Ability to speak is the main goal of communication in any language. The ability to cooperate and solve tasks together also comes to the fore. In the course of teaching a foreign language, many other very important questions arise:

- How to make the learning process informative and fun?

- How to solve the time pressure problem?

- How to make students with different potential acquire great knowledge and skills?

You can study in a team where strong students always win. You can perform individual tasks where no one will help a weak student. And you can learn when there are students nearby, from whom you can find out all the incomprehensible questions .

The effectiveness of teaching a foreign language depends on the joint coordinated activities of the teacher and students .

One of the most successful technologies for developing communication skills is collaborative learning technology. It allows you to find answers to the above questions

and optimize the learning process as much as possible. The effectiveness of this technology is especially visible in secondary or primary vocational education, that is, in a technical school. Students with different levels of learning gather here . There are those who have practically zero knowledge. It is very difficult for them to work individually. This is where small groups come to the rescue.

The main idea behind collaboration is learning together, not just doing things together. The main purpose of this technology is to create conditions for active learning activities of students in different learning situations. In a favorable atmosphere, the maximum realization of their capabilities takes place. Students are united in groups of several people. Each group has one task for all and a common goal. Emphasis is placed on group goals and the success of the whole group, which is achieved as a result of the independent work of each member of the group in constant interaction with other members of the same group when working on the topic (problem). The whole group is interested in the assimilation of information by each of its members, since their success depends on the contribution of each. It is collective learning, where there is interdependence that helps you achieve your goals. The team becomes the main force influencing the educational process. Communication skills are formed. The guys learn to work and create together, to be always ready to help others. Collaborative creative activity helps students become partners. The main form of such activity is joint communicative and cognitive activity. In cooperation, it is important not only to master the knowledge, skills and abilities of each student. The effect of socialization is important here. Students have new social roles. The teacher and students work together to develop goals, give grades in a collaborative state.

Collaboration helps the learner to acquire knowledge and methods of activity, communication experience. This will help him to work both in a large team and in a small group and individually.

Collaborative learning technology involves:

- ✓ interdependence of group members

- ✓ personal responsibility of each member of the group for their own successes and the successes of their comrades
- ✓ joint educational and cognitive activities
- ✓ overall assessment of the group.

Each student has an equal opportunity to succeed. Everyone is improving their own achievements. This gives advanced, intermediate and lagging learners an equal opportunity to earn points for their team.

Any job is constructed so that every participant is actively working for some time at rehydrating the interaction of students and teachers. The teacher creates a favorable environment for communication, he is an accomplice in communication, but also his coordinator.

How do I organize training on this technology?

1. The layout of the premises should change , the participants in the communication see each other. Tables should be placed at an angle if there are 3 people in groups or moved if there are 4 people

2. Students should be involved in cooperation gradually. They must understand why they need any skill.

3. The goal must be clear to the learner. The roles should also be clear.

Particular work is being done to form groups. They can be mixed (strong, medium and weak) or homogeneous (the level of students is the same).

When selecting groups, I take into account

1. The level of training .
2. Academic interests.
3. Extracurricular interests
4. Personal experience.
5. Sociability
6. The number of choices (the number of students willing to work with this student).

At the initial stages of work on the technology of cooperation, a lot of time is spent on psychological and pedagogical trainings aimed at: acquaintance of students with each other, team building, development of the ability to conduct a dialogue, discussion.

After completing the assignments by all groups, a collective discussion is organized. The task of the teacher is to monitor the activity in the groups. Control can be carried out orally (a speaker from the group) or in writing (test). If a test is carried out, then the marks are summed up, if the speaker is speaking, then his mark is an estimate for everyone.

Work in small groups according to the method of cooperation can be organized for the formation of lexical or grammatical skills or when monitoring the formation of skills in monologue, dialogical speech or when working with texts.

I will give a few examples of how this can be done.

Formation of lexical skills. After getting acquainted with the new vocabulary, students work in groups. They are engaged in spelling or vocabulary work (they find synonyms, antonyms for new vocabulary, form new words based on derivational elements). When doing spelling exercises for new words, it is usually the strong student who dictates and the rest try to write it down. If they make a mistake, they write again. At the end, students complete a written assignment "on the turntable", which they report to.

Development of reading skills with general content coverage. The task represents the answers to questions about the text. 2-3 questions are formulated for each student of the group. The most difficult one is for the strong one, let him answer first. Another student must find confirmation (refutation) of the answers of the first student in the text, and the third student must record these answers, find in the text or come up with examples that confirm (refute) the stated idea. Students in a circle change roles. Thus, they jointly provide answers to all questions and from their group present them for discussion to the group.

When working with large texts, you can organize the work according to the "saw" method. The text is divided into semantic parts. Each member of the group studies their

part. Then students studying the same part of the text meet and exchange information. This is called an “expert meeting”. Then they return to their groups and talk about everything new that they have learned. You need to listen carefully to each other and take notes. Each individual and the whole team as a whole report on the topic.

What does the cooperation technology teaching method give to students ?

- Prepares for project activities (develops the ability to conduct discussions, discuss various options for solving problems, build the logic of research)
- Knowledge sharing takes place in a more comfortable environment. Students turn to their peers, not the teacher.
- This form of work develops the ability to work in a team, teaches to communicate with each other, develops a sense of camaraderie, mutual assistance.
- When there is success, interest in the subject increases.
- Students learn to analyze their actions.
- In the course of joint cognitive activity, collectively new knowledge is constructed and it is better assimilated.

Literature :

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